

Observations on the Kalahari ground spider *Asemesthes subnubilus* Simon, 1887 (Araneae: Gnaphosidae)

Charles Haddad¹, Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman², Cecile Roux³ & Peter Webb³

¹University of the Free State, Bloemfontein; ²Department of Zoology, University of Venda; ³SANSa team members

ABSTRACT: The flat-bellied ground spiders of the genus *Asemesthes* Simon, 1887 are represented by 26 species, of which 25 are known from Southern Africa and 18 from South Africa. Although commonly sampled, little is still known about their behaviour. *Asemesthes subnubilus* Simon, 1887, commonly known as the Kalahari ground spider, was sampled from several localities in the Northern and Western Cape provinces of South Africa. The general morphology of both sexes is discussed, with notes on their behaviour, distribution and conservation status.

Key words: biodiversity, distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), Succulent Karoo Biome

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Asemesthes* Simon, 1887, represented by 26 species, is known from Angola, Namibia and South Africa, with only a single species described from Ethiopia (World Spider Catalog, 2022). As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), spiders were sampled throughout the country over a period of 23 years (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). A large number of *Asemesthes* specimens were sampled during pitfall surveys, and among them *A. subnubilus* Simon, 1887 has been identified. The general morphology of both sexes is discussed, with notes on their behaviour, distribution and conservation status.

METHODS

As part of SANSa, requests were made for photographs of spiders for the SANSa Virtual Museum (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012) and several sets of photographs of *A. subnubilus* were received from the public. Voucher specimens sampled during SANSa surveys are housed in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the Agricultural Research Council (ARC) in Pretoria.

TAXONOMIC NOTES

Asemesthes subnubilus Simon, 1887

Asemesthes subnubilus Simon, 1887: 373 (juv); Simon, 1893: 384, 340; Dalmas, 1921: 317, (juv); Tucker, 1923: 301; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2010: 287.

Asemesthes aureus Purcell, 1908: 242; Dalmas, 1921: 317 (synonym); Tucker, 1923: 288.

Asemesthes subnubilus, the type species of *Asemesthes*, is a Southern African endemic described by Simon (1887) from the Kalahari, but unfortunately based on juvenile specimens. A second species, *A. aureus*, described by Purcell (1908) from the Kalahari too, was synonymised with *A. subnubilus* by Dalmas (1921). The only drawing available of the species is the eye pattern by Dalmas (1921). However, the presence of golden setae across the body without pronounced darker markings, noted in several descriptions, is found in only a single *Asemesthes* species on the subcontinent.

Diagnostic characteristics: Female: total length 5–6mm. Carapace integument dark brown, clothed with fawn to yellow appressed setae (Figs 1-4), in some with intermingled white setae (Fig. 9); fovea not distinct (Fig. 3); clypeus with strong, forward-directed setae (Fig. 3). Eyes in two rows; anterior row only slightly procurved, slightly wider than posterior row; posterior row strongly recurved; lateral eyes larger than median eyes in both rows; median eyes smaller than lateral eyes; anterior lateral eyes largest, followed by posterior lateral eyes, with posterior median eyes smallest; median ocular quadrangle longer than wide, narrower posteriorly (Figs 1, 3).

Figures 1–4. *Asemesthes subnubilus*: 1,3 Female and 2. Male from Aardvark Nature Reserve. 4. Male from Richtersveld. Photo credits: 1–3. Peter Webb. 4. Charles Haddad.

Figures 5–8. *Asemesthes subnubilus*: 5. Female habitus, dorsal view. 6. Male habitus, dorsal view. 7. Male palp, ventral view. 8. Female epigyne, ventral view. Photos: Charles Haddad.

Abdomen integument brown, clothed with golden-yellow appressed setae; spinnerets darker (Fig. 9). Legs dark, with similar appressed setae as carapace, but less dense; all legs with numerous erect scattered setae, but tarsi paler. Epigyne (Fig. 8): with tongue-like median scape and atrium broader than long. Male: total length: 4-5 mm. Similar to female, but slightly darker, more slender and smaller in size (Fig. 6). Palp (Fig. 7): tegulum ovoid, embolus originating proximally, curving around prolateral margin, associated with membranous conductor distally.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

South Africa, Namibia.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

SOUTH AFRICA. Northern Cape: Kamaggas (-29.75, 17.40); Steinkopf (-29.25, 17.73.); Richtersveld Transfrontier National Park (-28.25, 17.17); Namaqua National Park (-30.017, 17.579); Akkerendam Nature Reserve (-31.433, 19.783); Upington (-28.435, 21.305); Jakkalsputs (-28.67, 16.95); Tankwa-Karoo National Park (-32.28, 19.82). **Western Cape:** Aardvark Nature Reserve (-33.494, 21.088).

BEHAVIOUR

Asemesthes subnubilus are free-running ground dwellers and they were sampled from the Succulent Karoo Biome. In Upington the species was observed in a sandy patch. They were found in small burrows made in the sand. A silk funnel covers the entrance with plant matter sometimes sticking to the silk (Fig. 11). The spiders can be seen in the burrow (Fig. 12) but they are shy and are not easy to catch. At the Aardvark Nature Reserve the entrance to a burrow was photograph showing the shape and area it covers (Fig. 10).

Figures 9–13. *Asemesthes subnubilus*: 9. Female, dorsal view of body. 10. Burrow with funnel-shaped silk entrance. 11. Female in burrow. 12. Female in burrow entrance. 13. Female, dorsal view. Photo credits: 9–10. Peter Webb; 11–12. Cecile Roux. 13. Judd Kirkel.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We thank Judd Kinkel for the use of his photo.

REFERENCES

- DALMAS R. DE 1921. Monographie des araignées de la section des Pterotracha (Aran. Gnaphosidae). *Annales de la Société Entomologique de France* 89: 233–328.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H., LYLE R., LOTZ L.N., HELBERG L., MATHEBULA S., VAN DEN BERG A., VAN DEN BERG A.M., VAN NIEKERK E. & JOCQUÉ R. 2010. *First Atlas of the Spiders of South Africa*. South African National Survey of Arachnida. SANSa Technical Report version 1 (2010): 1158 pp.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H., LYLE R., LOTZ L.N. & MARAIS P. 2015. South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa): review of current knowledge, constraints and future needs for documenting spider diversity (Arachnida: Araneae). *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 70(3): 245–275.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H. & LOTZ L.N. 2021. The Gnaphosidae of South Africa, version 1. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, version 2: 268 pp.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., LYLE R. & VAN DEN BERG A.M. 2012. Bioinformatics on the spiders of South Africa. *Serket* 13(1/2): 121–127.
- PURCELL W.F. 1908. Araneae (I). In: Schultze, L. (ed.): Zoologische und anthropologische Ergebnisse einer Forschungsreise im westlichen und zentralen Südafrika. Erster Band: Systematik und Tiergeographie. Zweite Lieferung. *Denkschriften der Medizinisch-Naturwissenschaftlichen Gesellschaft zu Jena* 13: 203–246, pp. 11.
- SIMON E. 1887. Etudes arachnologiques. 20e Mémoire. XXVIII. Arachnides recueillis dans le sud de l'Afrique par M. le docteur Hans Schinz. *Annales de la Société Entomologique de France* (6) 7: 369–384.
- SIMON E. 1893. *Histoire naturelle des araignées*. Deuxième édition, tome premier. Roret, Paris, pp. 257–488.
- TUCKER R.W.E. 1923. The Drassidae of South Africa. *Annals of the South African Museum* 19: 251–437.